

**METHOD AND TOOL TO EVALUATE EARLY
CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR AND YOUTH SPORT
COACH LEARNING, TEACHING TRAINING EVENTS
AND TEACHING UNITS**

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TECHNICAL SHEET

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Website: <https://edupass-project.eu/>

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Education for Physical Activity and Sport: Informal and Non-formal Settings (EduPASS) programme has developed thus far important Results (R). The main R are:

- R#1 – Overview on Educator and Coach Education and Training in Europe
- R#2 – Recommendations on Educator and Coach Education and Training
- R#3 – Educator and Coach Profile
- R#4 – Theoretical and Methodological Framework for Educator and Coach Education and Training
- R#5 – Modular programme for Educator and Coach Education and Training Consisting of Courses and Teaching Units

Following the previously developed outputs, the aim of this R#6 is to develop a method and tool(s) to evaluate Early Childhood Educator (ECE) and Youth Sport Coach (YSC) events, courses and teaching units. The teaching units were developed by the partner experts, were informed by their work at the respective Institutions and the outcomes of R#1 - R#5. All teaching units were open to an evaluation process at the Learning and Teaching Training (LTT) events¹ in Dublin and Luxembourg. Table 1 presents the teaching units which were evaluated during the LTT events. This R consists of two different systematic evaluation tools assessing the quality of the teaching units developed in R#5: from the perspectives of (1) Youth Sport Coach Educators (YSC-E), as experts; and (2) Youth Sport Coaches (YSC), as target group for learning. Each of those distinct, systematic evaluation tools was then adapted to fit the context of Early Childhood Educators. Thus, two additional evaluation tools for teaching unit assessment were developed, for Early Childhood Educator Developers (ECE-D) as experts, and Early Childhood Educators (ECE) as learners, respectively.

A specific, tailor-made EduPASS evaluation method and tool(s) for the purpose of this project did not exist thus far. However, a previous Erasmus+ programme on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education in Europe (PRIME PETE) developed a method and tool (Adamakis, Scheuer, Carraro, & Santi, 2023), which could be used as a reference point for the development of the current instruments. Thus, the PRIME PETE method and tool were adapted and used to suit the needs and requirements of the EduPASS programme and settings.

The overall purpose of this evaluation process was to: (1) provide a tool to evaluate teaching units; (2) provide evaluations of the teaching units at the first LTT event in Dublin to feed forward to the planning, design, development, and delivery of further teaching units at the following LTT event in Luxembourg; (3) inform the readers of the evaluation process; and (4) highlight the feedback received via the evaluation tool related to the teaching units; hence, the evaluation process can inform the potential users of the EduPASS website and materials. Additionally, the developed EduPASS evaluation tools will be used in the following R (i.e., R#7), which is the evaluation study

¹ A **Learning and Teaching Training** event brings together educators, trainers, learners, and stakeholders, and typically focuses on enhancing educators' instructional skills and pedagogical strategies. It aims to provide them with new insights, techniques, and approaches to improve their teaching effectiveness and student engagement.

and respective report. In addition, the method and tool(s) can be used in future, similar evaluation procedures. The R content is developed only in English language.

Table 1. Teaching units under evaluation during the LTT events

Teaching units delivered in Dublin LTT event	Teaching units delivered in Luxembourg LTT event
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I Coach Kids Pledge • The Youth Sport Compass – The 4 Pillars (parts 1 and 2) • Coaching Practice • Youth Sport Compass and Coaching Practice • Coaching Girls: A Practical Emphasis • Young Voices Toolkit • Debrief of Primary School Coaching Session • Coaching Skills – Plan, Organise, Demo, Comms, Observe, Feedback, Reflection • Understanding Physical Literacy 1 (parts 1 and 2) • Your Personal Coaching Toolkit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FUNdamental Play • Fundamental Movement Skills • Inclusive Teaching in Physical Education • I Educate Kids • PA Educator Toolkit • Motor Ability Assessment: Motor Abilities in Childhood and Youth • PA Educator Toolkit • MOBAK Assessment • Importance of Daily PA for Health Promotion

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The theoretical background, as well as the overall development procedure and validity testing of the tool was based on Adamakis, Scheuer, Carraro and Santi (2023) report. Developing a tool in the form of a questionnaire to evaluate teaching units requires a systematic approach that takes into account the specific learning outcomes of the teaching units. The steps that can be followed to develop an effective questionnaire are:

- Identify the learning outcomes of the teaching unit(s). Before developing a questionnaire, it is important to clearly define the learning outcomes of the teaching units(s). This can be done by reviewing the teaching units' indicative content, and any other relevant materials.
- Choose a relevant evaluation framework or model. There are several evaluation frameworks and models available that can be used to guide the development of an evaluation questionnaire, such as the Kirkpatrick Model, the Learning Transfer Evaluation Model, Brinkerhoff's Success Case Method, Anderson Model of Learning Evaluation, the CIRO Model, the Phillips ROI Model, Kaufman's Model of Learning Evaluation, etc. Out of these models, the Kirkpatrick Model (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006), was selected, which is a widely used framework that includes four levels of evaluation: reaction, learning, behaviour, and results.

- Determine the type of questions to ask. Depending on the evaluation framework or model chosen, the types of questions to be included in the questionnaire will vary. For example, if using the Kirkpatrick Model, questions related to most evaluation levels should be included.
- Use specific references to inform the questions. To ensure that the questions are relevant and aligned with the learning outcomes of the teaching unit(s), it can be helpful to use specific references such as the module indicative content or learning materials. These references can inform the development of questions related to the content, instructional strategies, and assessment methods used in the teaching unit(s).
- Pilot test the questionnaire. Before administering the tool to all participants, it is important to pilot test it with a small group to identify any issues or areas for improvement.

By following these steps, a tool in the form of a questionnaire can be developed that effectively evaluates the teaching units and provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of the learning experience.

Kirkpatrick and Kirkpatrick (2006) proposed a widely used framework for evaluating the effectiveness of training programmes. The Kirkpatrick Model consists of four levels of evaluation: reaction, learning, behaviour, and results. The initial level of evaluation concerns the participants' immediate responses to the training programme, whereas the subsequent level examines the extent of knowledge and skill acquisition that has occurred during the training period. The third level of evaluation assesses the extent to which participants have integrated the knowledge and skills acquired during the training programme into their professional performance. The fourth level gauges the impact of the training programme on the organization's overall goals and objectives.

The Kirkpatrick Model has gained considerable popularity as a means of evaluating the efficacy of training programmes within organisational contexts. It offers a comprehensive approach to assessment that considers both immediate and long-term outcomes. The utilisation of this model enables organisations to identify areas for improvement, make evidence-based decisions regarding future training initiatives and demonstrate the value of their training investments to stakeholders.

The Kirkpatrick Model comprises the initial level of evaluation, which assesses the reactions of participants to the training programme. The objective of this level is to ascertain the level of satisfaction and acceptance of the programme among the participants. The evaluation assesses participants' perceptions of the training experience, including the relevance of the training content, the quality of the instruction, and the overall training environment. The level of satisfaction and acceptance is of major importance, as it provides organisations with invaluable insight into the quality of their programmes and enables them to ascertain the extent to which the programme aligns with the expectations of the participants. Furthermore, it can affect participants' motivation to engage in subsequent training programmes and can also influence their attitudes towards the organisation and their role. Overall, the level of satisfaction and acceptance as defined by the Kirkpatrick Model is an essential aspect of evaluating the effectiveness of training programmes, as it enables organisations to identify areas for improvement and to ensure that their training programmes are meeting the needs of their participants.

The Kirkpatrick Model (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006) does not explicitly include self-assessed learning progress as a component. Nevertheless, it can be considered as a component of the second level of evaluation, which assesses the extent to which participants have acquired knowledge and skills during the training programme. At this level, participants are evaluated based on their capacity to apply the knowledge and skills acquired through the assessment of tests, examinations, or other evaluation methods. Furthermore, self-assessment can be employed as a means of gauging learning progress, as it enables participants to engage in introspective reflection on their learning processes and identify areas requiring further development. The utilisation of self-assessment can prove to be a beneficial instrument for both the participants and the organisations in question. For the participants, it can facilitate self-reflection and encourage them to assume responsibility for their own learning. For organisations, it can provide supplementary data for the evaluation of the efficacy of their training programmes, thus facilitating the identification of potential areas for improvement. Consequently, this evaluation process, which incorporates a second level of evaluation, is deemed an adequate fit for the EduPASS programme and settings.

The assessment of behavioural change is included as the third level of evaluation in the Kirkpatrick Model (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006). This level aims to measure the extent to which participants have applied what they learned during the training programme to their individual performance. To illustrate, in the context of teacher training, the assessment of behavioural change may entail the observation of teachers in the classroom and the evaluation of their implementation of novel instructional strategies acquired during the training programme. Furthermore, data may be collected on student outcomes to ascertain whether the newly implemented instructional strategies are positively influencing learning outcomes. The assessment of behavioural change constitutes an essential element in the evaluation of the efficacy of training programmes, as it enables organisations to ascertain whether participants are capable of applying the knowledge and skills acquired in actual work contexts. Furthermore, insights may be gained into the factors that may facilitate or hinder the transfer of learning from the training programme to the workplace. In essence, the assessment of behavioural change represents a pivotal element of the Kirkpatrick Model, offering indispensable insights into the efficacy of teacher training programmes. By elucidating whether the training is engendering meaningful changes in teacher behaviour, this assessment provides invaluable data that can inform the enhancement of student learning outcomes. It can therefore be concluded that the selection of the Kirkpatrick Model as a suitable model to inform the development of the EduPASS evaluation tools is appropriate (similar to the PRIME PETE evaluation tools).

The development of the EduPASS questionnaire for the participants was informed by the three of the four levels of evaluation proposed by Kirkpatrick and Kirkpatrick (2006). These three levels included "satisfaction and acceptance", "self-assessed learning progress", and "assessment of behavioural change through the teacher training". The category "satisfaction and acceptance" was divided into two subcategories: "satisfaction and acceptance regarding the content" and "satisfaction and acceptance regarding the teacher training".

3 DEVELOPMENT PROCEDURE AND EVIDENCE OF VALIDITY

In addition to the implementation of Kirkpatrick's Model, a review process of previously developed questionnaires that evaluate University and Institution teaching units in the EduPASS partner institutions was implemented. The Universities and partners' administrations responsible for EduPASS teaching unit evaluations were contacted, and the respective websites and online learning platforms were checked. All project partners and fellow colleagues were contacted and asked to provide their insights based on their own experiences with previous questionnaires. This was considered to be an adequate procedure to gain insights into what has worked well and what needs improvement in past module evaluation questionnaires.

Following this procedure, two initial draft questionnaires were developed (one for YSCs and one for YSC-E) by the main project team to assess the teaching units, as well as the LTT events. These initial questionnaires and respective items went through three feedback rounds, where all project partners participated. The questionnaires were adapted and improved based on feedback from reports, subsequent group discussions and through expert meetings. The final questionnaires were based on a larger pool of test items developed and discussed in several expert meetings. This process of developing the various items may be understood as a design step for maintaining face and content validity.

To ensure the face and content validity of the items and questionnaires, all project partners, who are experts in EduPASS since they hold high academic and administrative positions in their respective Universities and Institutions, participated in the discussion and feedback process. Face validity is an informal review of a questionnaire by experts, who assess its clarity, comprehensibility, and appropriateness for the target-group, whilst content validity involves a formal assessment by subject experts, to determine appropriateness of content and identify any misunderstandings or omissions (Tanner, 2018; Thomas, Martin, Etnier, & Silverman, 2023). Also, Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) defined content validity as the degree to which a measure's items represent a proper sample of the theoretical content domain of a construct. For the criterion of content validity to be met by the initial pool of items, these items need to be face valid. Face validity has been defined as reflecting the extent to which a measure reflects what it is intended to measure (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Furthermore, expert judging was not used as a substitute for the scale development process. Rather, expert judging was used, as stated by Hardesty and Bearden (2004), to obtain some justification for the face validity of items when those items are not the focal point of the research. Moreover, project partners evaluated the appearance of the questionnaires in terms of feasibility, readability, consistency of style and formatting, and the clarity of the language used. During the final feedback round, all project partners agreed that the questionnaires measure what they have been designed to measure, as well as the questionnaires include items that assess every domain of the construct, thus face and construct validity were established.

Subsequently, the valid questionnaires implemented at the LTT in Dublin, were then adapted to fit the ECE context and setting, substituting certain wording and terminology.

4 QUESTIONNAIRES

The final version of the questionnaires (one for Youth Sport Coaches and one for Youth Sport Coach Educators, subsequently also one version for ECE and one for ECE-D) was divided into three main sections.

- Demographic information: respondents were required to provide their socio-demographic details such as age, gender, country of residence, sport participation, years of coaching experience, coach training attendance, etc.
- Evaluation of the LTT event: this section contained items regarding the organisational aspects (5 items), teaching and content (11 items for YSC/ECE and 16 items for YSC-E/ECE-D), implementation and feasibility of the event (5 items), and one item about recommending the event to peers. For all items a five-point Likert-type scale was used, ranging from disagree (1) to agree (5), and a not applicable (N/A) answer was also available. Additionally, to gain a deeper insight and understanding in what the participants thought about the event, four open-ended questions were included regarding the best features of the event, things the participants did not like, potential changes that could be implemented, and specific comments about the LTT event.
- Evaluation of the teaching units: this section contained items regarding the learning, teaching, assessment, feedback, workload, skills development, management, learning environment and overall satisfaction with the teaching unit (26 items). For all items a five-point Likert-type scale was used, ranging from very dissatisfied (1) to very satisfied (5), and a not applicable (N/A) answer was also available. Furthermore, one additional question was used about recommending the teaching unit to peers, with possible answers ranging from disagree (1) to agree (5). Similar to the previous section, four open-ended questions were included regarding the best features of the teaching unit, things the participants did not like, potential changes that could be implemented, and specific comments about the teaching unit. All questionnaires and all items are presented in detail in the *Appendix*.

The participants were provided with detailed information and instructions about the completion of the questionnaires. In addition, they were informed that the questionnaire completion was voluntary, all information provided would be confidential and participants' anonymity would be protected throughout the entire procedure. Furthermore, all collected data would be stored securely in accordance with current data protection regulations (European General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 of 27/4/2016) and only project partners would have access to this data stored in Microsoft OneDrive (a cloud system used by the University of Luxembourg and the Willibald Gebhardt Research Institute based on the universities' servers). The results of the evaluation process will be published without sharing any information about the respondents in an open access publication in the frame of the EduPASS programme. Finally, all data will be retained for a minimum period of 5 years following the completion of the project. Following this period, all data will be destroyed.

5 CONCLUSION

The aim of the present R#6 was to develop EduPASS evaluation tools for the LTT events and the corresponding teaching units of the EduPASS programme. A well-designed evaluation tool can assist organisations, stakeholders as well as individual YSC-E/ECE-D in assessing the efficacy of their pedagogical approaches, identifying areas for enhancement, and providing constructive feedback to learners. The development of an evaluation tool should be informed by a considered approach to the learning outcomes, the content of the module, and the assessment criteria.

The EduPASS evaluation tools are designed in a way that aligns with the outcomes of the events and the teaching units, as well as the desired learning outcomes. In addition, it was ensured that the EduPASS evaluation tools are user-friendly and accessible to all educators, regardless of their background or abilities, and they were tested for face and content validity, meaning that they consistently measure what they are supposed to measure. To ensure the effectiveness of the EduPASS evaluation tools, they should undergo thorough testing and further validation. This will assist to identify any potential issues or areas for improvement and refine the tools to make them more effective.

Overall, the development of effective evaluation tools for teaching units is of paramount importance for the enhancement of teaching and learning quality. Such a system provides valuable feedback to both educators and students, facilitating the identification of areas for improvement and the development of effective teaching strategies. It is therefore imperative that time and resources are allocated to the development of bespoke evaluation tools that are fit for purpose for both students and educators.

6 REFERENCES

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APPENDIX

EduPASS Learning, Teaching Training event and teaching unit evaluation tool for Youth Sport Coaches (YSC)

Please help enhance the quality of the YSC Learning, Teaching and Training event and the teaching units by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Participation in this evaluation is voluntary. All information provided will be confidential and participants' anonymity will be protected throughout the evaluation process. IP addresses will not be collected at any point, meaning the data you provide cannot be traced back to the participant. The results of the evaluation process will be used without sharing any information about the respondents.

Part 1: General information

1.1. What is your age?

1.2. What is your gender?

1.3. Country

1.4. University / Faculty / Department / Organisation

1.5. Are you currently practising any sport? Yes No

1.6. Have you practised any sport in the past? Yes No

1.7. If you answered **YES** in one of the previous questions (1.5 and/or 1.6), what is/was the main sport that you have been practicing?

Type of sport: _____

1.8. How many years have you been practicing this sport?

_____ years

1.9. What is your major achievement in this sport (e.g., awards, competitions on local, district, regional, national, international level)?

1.10. Do you currently work as Youth Sport Coach? Yes No

1.11. Have you worked as a Youth Sport Coach in the past? Yes No

1.12. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), what is/was the main sport that you have been coaching?

Type of sport: _____

1.13. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), for how many years have you been a Youth Sport Coach?

_____ years

1.14. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), what age groups do you primarily coach?

Children (under the age of 12 years)

Adolescents (ages 13-17 years old)

Young adults (18-25 years)

Adults (over 25 years)

Part 2: Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event

To ensure the quality of the event as well as improving the training, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions. Please select the most relevant answer for each statement.

2.1. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event?

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
Organisational aspects						
2.1.1	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.2	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.3	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.4	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.5	<input type="radio"/>					
Teaching and content						
2.1.6	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.7	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.8	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.9	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.10	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.11	<input type="radio"/>					

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.1.12 The content will be helpful to me as a Youth Sport Coach.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.13 The teaching units of the event are compatible with the national coaching framework.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.14 I gained new knowledge and information for my coaching practice from the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.15 The topic and content presented in the event was new to me.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.16 I enjoyed the event.	<input type="radio"/>					

2.2. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the implementation and feasibility of the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event?

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.2.1	The event motivated me to consider implementing the contents in my coaching.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.2	I will use the materials and resources which I received in the event in my future career as a Youth Sport Coach.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.3	I can imagine myself implementing EduPASS resources in my future career as a Youth Sport Coach.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.4	I believe that the sport club environment will be supportive for the implementation of the EduPASS resources.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.5	I consider the EduPASS resources useful as they can be easily implemented during coaching.	<input type="radio"/>					

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
2.3.	I would recommend this Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event to other Youth Sport Coaches.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future Youth Sport Coaches. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event that you think is relevant.

The **BEST** features of the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following **CHANGES**:

I have specific comments for this Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event:

Teaching unit Title:	Teaching unit Code:
-----------------------------	----------------------------

Date:

Part 3: Teaching unit content

3.1. Indicate your level of satisfaction with each of the following items by selecting the most relevant answer.

	1 ☹	2	3	4	5 ☺	N/A
RATING: 1 = Very Dissatisfied 2 = Dissatisfied 3 = Neutral 4 = Satisfied 5 = Very Satisfied						
3.1.1 The overall teaching of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.2 The delivery of the teaching unit (e.g., lectures, practical sessions, group discussions, sharing of ideas and experiences, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.3 The pedagogical approaches presented to coaching sports.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.4 The description of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.5 The content of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.6 The clarity of the teaching unit content.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.7 The balance between theory and practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.8 The defined learning outcomes and/or objectives were adequately explained.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.9 The learning materials (e.g., handouts, workshop material, case studies, websites, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.10 The appropriateness of the assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.11 The explanation of the assessment criteria.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.12 The assessment methods effectiveness in identifying my strengths and areas for future development.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.13 The communication of the learning outcomes and assessment model.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.14 The collaboration through shared knowledge with peers.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.15 The overall workload (achievable, realistic, adequate).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.16 The effectiveness of the module in raising my professional development.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.17 The quality of the support given by the teaching staff on assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					

3.1.18	The preparation of the teaching staff.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.19	The approachability and support of the teaching staff (i.e., instructive, inspiring, encouraging, and motivating).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.20	The organisational arrangements for the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.21	The relevance of the teaching unit to raising my professional development (knowledge and practice).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.22	The transferability of the lessons learnt in the teaching unit to practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.23	The development of new skills and/or teaching strategies due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.24	The increase of my motivation to learn due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.25	The overall knowledge gained by the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.26	My overall satisfaction with the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
3.2. I would recommend this teaching unit to other sport educators.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the teaching unit

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future Youth Sport Coaches. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the teaching unit that you think is relevant.

The BEST features of the teaching unit were:

I did NOT like the following:

I would like to see the following CHANGES:

I have specific comments for this teaching unit:

I will try to implement these teaching unit's topics (maximum 3) in my coaching practice:

EduPASS Youth Sport Coaches Learning, Teaching Training event and teaching unit evaluation tool for Youth Sport Coach Educators (YSC-E)

Please help enhance the quality of the Youth Sport Coaches Learning, Teaching Training event and the teaching units by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Participation in this evaluation is voluntary. All information provided will be confidential and participants' anonymity will be protected throughout the evaluation. IP addresses will not be collected at any point, meaning the data you provide cannot be traced back to the participant. The results of the evaluation process will be used without sharing any information about the respondents.

Part 1: General Information

1.1. What is your age?

1.2. What is your gender?

1.3. Country

1.4. University / Faculty / Department / Organisation

1.5. Are you currently practising any sport? Yes No

1.6. Have you practised any sport in the past? Yes No

1.7. If you answered **YES** in one of the previous questions (1.5 and/or 1.6), what is/was the main sport that you have been practicing?

Type of sport: _____

1.8. How many years have you been practicing this sport?

_____ years

1.9. What is your major achievement in this sport (e.g., awards, competitions on local, district, regional, national, international level)?

1.10. Are you currently a Youth Sport Coach Educator? Yes No

1.11. Have you worked as a Youth Sport Coach Educator in the past? Yes No

1.12. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), in which sport(s) have you been a Youth Sport Coach Educator?

Type of sport(s): _____

1.13. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), for how many years have you been a Youth Sport Coach Educator?

_____ years

1.14. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), which topic(s)/module(s) have you been teaching?

1.15. Do you currently work as a Youth Sport Coach? Yes No

1.16. Have you worked in the past as a Youth Sport Coach? Yes No

1.17. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.15 and/or 1.16), what is/was the main sport that you have been coaching?

1.18. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.15 and/or 1.16), for how many years have you been a Youth Sport Coach?

_____ years

1.19. If you answered **YES** in the previous question (1.15 and/or 1.16), what age groups do you primarily coach?

Children (under the age of 12 years)

Adolescents (ages 13-17 years old)

Young adults (18-25 years)

Adults (over 25 years)

1.20. If you answered **YES** in the previous question (1.15 and/or 1.16), what is the athletes' level that you primarily coach?

Recreational

Competitive

Elite

Professional

Part 2: Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event

To ensure the quality of the event as well as improving it, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions. Please select the most relevant answer for each statement.

2.1. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event?

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
Organisational aspects						
2.1.1 The event was adequately and logically structured.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.2 The event was well designed.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.3 The time frame of the event was appropriate.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.4 The event was delivered at an appropriate pace/rhythm.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.5 The materials and resources were well prepared.	<input type="radio"/>					
Teaching and content						
2.1.6 The content was presented in a clear and understandable way.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.7 The teaching enabled the learners to attain the learning outcomes.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.8 The learners seemed to enjoy the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.9 The learners engaged and actively participated during the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.10 The overall topic of the event referred well to the practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.11 The specific content of the event referred well to the practice.	<input type="radio"/>					

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.1.12 The topics were discussed sufficiently.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.13 I was able to improve my knowledge and skills related to the topics discussed.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.14 The content will be helpful to me as a Youth Sport Coach educator.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.15 The teaching units of the event are compatible with the national coaching framework.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.16 I gained new knowledge and information for my coaching practice from the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.18 The topic and content presented in the event was new to me.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.19 I enjoyed the event.	<input type="radio"/>					

2.2. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the implementation and feasibility of the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event?

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.2.1	The event motivated me to consider implementing the contents in my coaching.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.2	I will use the materials and resources which I received in the event in my future sessions and coaching.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.3	I can imagine myself implementing EduPASS resources with other future Youth Sport Coaches.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.4	I believe that the sport club environment will be supportive for the implementation of the EduPASS resources.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.5	I consider the EduPASS resources useful as they can be easily implemented during coaching.	<input type="radio"/>					

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
2.3.	I would recommend this Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event to other sport and coach educators.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future Youth Sport Coaches. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event that you think is relevant.

The **BEST** features of the Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following **CHANGES**:

I have specific comments for this Youth Sport Coach Learning, Teaching Training event:

Teaching unit Title:	Teaching unit Code:
-----------------------------	----------------------------

Date:

Part 3: Teaching unit content

3.2. Indicate your level of satisfaction with each of the following items by selecting the most relevant answer.

	1 ☹	2	3	4	5 ☺	N/A
RATING: 1 = Very Dissatisfied 2 = Dissatisfied 3 = Neutral 4 = Satisfied 5 = Very Satisfied						
3.1.1 The overall teaching of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.2 The delivery of the teaching unit (e.g., lectures, practical sessions, group discussions, sharing of ideas and experiences, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.3 The pedagogical approaches presented to coaching sports.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.4 The description of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.5 The content of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.6 The clarity of the teaching unit content.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.7 The balance between theory and practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.8 The defined learning outcomes and/or objectives were adequately explained.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.9 The learning materials (e.g., handouts, workshop material, case studies, websites, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.10 The appropriateness of the assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.11 The explanation of the assessment criteria.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.12 The assessment methods effectiveness in identifying Youth Sport Coaches' strengths and areas for future development.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.13 The communication of the learning outcomes and assessment model.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.14 The collaboration through shared knowledge with peers.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.15 The overall workload (achievable, realistic, adequate).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.16 The effectiveness of the module in raising Youth Sport Coaches' professional development.	<input type="radio"/>					

3.1.17	The quality of the support given by the teaching staff on assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.18	The preparation of the teaching staff.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.19	The approachability and support of teaching staff (i.e., instructive, inspiring, encouraging, and motivating).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.20	The organisational arrangements for the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.21	The relevance of the teaching unit in raising Youth Sport Coaches' professional development (knowledge and practice).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.22	The transferability of the lessons learnt in the teaching unit to practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.23	The development of new skills and/or coaching strategies due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.24	The increase of my motivation to learn due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.25	The overall knowledge gained by the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.26	My overall satisfaction with the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
3.2. I would recommend this teaching unit to other Youth Sport Coaches and YSC Educators.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the teaching unit

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future Youth Sport Coaches. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the teaching unit that you think is relevant.

The **BEST** features of the teaching unit were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following **CHANGES**:

I have specific comments for this teaching unit:

I will try to implement these teaching unit's topics (maximum 3) in my coaching practice:

EduPASS Early Childhood Educators training event and teaching unit evaluation tool for Early Childhood Educators

Please help enhance the quality of the Early Childhood Educators training event and the teaching units by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Participation in this study is voluntary. All information provided will be confidential and participants' anonymity will be protected throughout the study. IP addresses will not be collected at any point, meaning the data you provide cannot be traced back to the participant. The results of the evaluation process will be published without sharing any information about the respondents in an open access publication in the frame of the EduPASS European project.

Part 1: General information

1.1. What is your age?

1.2. What is your gender?

1.3. Country

1.4. University / Faculty / Department / Organization

1.5. Are you currently practising any sport? Yes No

1.6. Have you practised any sport in the past? Yes No

1.7. If you answered **YES** in one of the previous questions (1.5 and/or 1.6), what is/was the main sport that you have been practicing?

Type of sport: _____

1.8. How many years have you been practicing this sport?

_____ years

1.9. What is your major achievement in this sport (e.g., awards, competitions on local, district, regional, national, international level)?

1.10. Do you currently work as early childhood educator? Yes No

1.11. Have you worked as early childhood educator in the past? Yes No

1.12. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), what is/was the main sport that you have been teaching?

Type of sport: _____

1.13. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), for how many years have you been an early childhood educator?

_____ years

1.14. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), what age groups do you primarily teach?

Children (under the age of 12 years)

Adolescents (ages 13-17 years old)

Young adults (18-25 years)

Adults (over 25 years)

1.15. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), what is the athletes' level that you primarily teach?

Recreational

Competitive

Elite

Professional

1.16. Have you attended any early childhood educator training/courses in the past? Yes No

1.17. If you have attended, briefly describe what this training was about.

1.18. Do you have a bachelor and/or master's (or respective equivalent academic university) degree in sport science and/or physical education?

No

Yes, I have a bachelor's degree

Yes, I have a master's degree

Yes, I have an equivalent academic university degree

Part 2: Early Childhood Educators training event

To ensure the quality of the event as well as improving the training, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions. Please select the most relevant answer for each statement.

2.1. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the early childhood educator training event?

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
Organizational aspects						
2.1.1 The event was adequately and logically structured.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.2 The event was well designed.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.3 The time frame of the event was appropriate.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.4 The event was delivered at an appropriate pace/rhythm.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.5 The materials and resources were well prepared.	<input type="radio"/>					
Teaching and content						
2.1.6 The content was presented in a clear and understandable way.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.7 The teaching enabled me to attain the learning outcomes.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.8 The overall topic of the event was relevant for my practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.9 The specific content of the event was relevant to my practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.10 The topics were discussed sufficiently.	<input type="radio"/>					

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.1.11	I was able to improve my knowledge and skills related to the topics discussed.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.12	The content will be helpful to me as a early childhood educator.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.13	The teaching units of the event are compatible with the national coaching framework.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.14	I gained new knowledge and information for my teaching practice from the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.15	The topic and content presented in the event was new to me.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.16	I enjoyed the event.	<input type="radio"/>					

2.2. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the implementation and feasibility of the early childhood educators training event?

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.2.1	The event motivated me to consider implementing the contents in my teaching.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.2	I will use the materials and resources which I received in the event in my future career as early childhood educator.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.3	I can imagine myself implementing EduPASS resources in my future career as early childhood educator.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.4	I believe that the sport club environment will be supportive for the implementation of the EduPASS resources.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.5	I consider the EduPASS resources useful as they can be easily implemented during teaching.	<input type="radio"/>					

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
2.3.	I would recommend this early childhood educators training event to other early childhood educators.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the early childhood educator training event

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future early childhood educators. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the early childhood educators training event that you think is relevant.

The BEST features of the early childhood educators training event were:

I did NOT like the following:

I would like to see the following CHANGES:

I have specific comments for this early childhood educators training event:

Teaching unit Title:	Teaching unit Code:
-----------------------------	----------------------------

Date:

Part 3: Teaching unit content

3.3. Indicate your level of satisfaction with each of the following items by selecting the most relevant answer.

	1 ☹	2	3	4	5 ☺	N/A
RATING: 1 = Very Dissatisfied 2 = Dissatisfied 3 = Neutral 4 = Satisfied 5 = Very Satisfied						
3.1.1 The overall teaching of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.2 The delivery of the teaching unit (e.g., lectures, practical sessions, group discussions, sharing of ideas and experiences, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.3 The pedagogical approaches presented to teaching sports.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.4 The description of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.5 The content of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.6 The clarity of the teaching unit content.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.7 The balance between theory and practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.8 The defined learning outcomes and/or objectives were adequately explained.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.9 The learning materials (e.g., handouts, workshop material, case studies, websites, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.10 The appropriateness of the assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.11 The explanation of the assessment criteria.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.12 The assessment methods effectiveness in identifying my strengths and areas for future development.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.13 The communication of the learning outcomes and assessment model.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.14 The collaboration through shared knowledge with peers.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.15 The overall workload (achievable, realistic, adequate).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.16 The effectiveness of the teaching unit in raising my professional development.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.17 The quality of the support given by the teaching staff on assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.18 The preparation of the teaching staff.	<input type="radio"/>					

3.1.19	The approachability and support of the teaching staff (i.e., instructive, inspiring, encouraging, and motivating).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.20	The organisational arrangements for the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.21	The relevance of the teaching unit to raising my professional development (knowledge and practice).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.22	The transferability of the lessons learnt in the teaching unit to practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.23	The development of new skills and/or teaching strategies due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.24	The increase of my motivation to learn due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.25	The overall knowledge gained by the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.26	My overall satisfaction with the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
3.2. I would recommend this teaching unit to other early childhood educators.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the teaching unit

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future early childhood educators. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the teaching unit that you think is relevant.

The **BEST** features of the teaching unit were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following **CHANGES**:

I have specific comments for this teaching unit:

I will try to implement these teaching unit's topics (maximum 3) in my teaching practice:

EduPASS Early Childhood Educators training event and teaching unit evaluation tool for Early Childhood Educator-Developers

Please help enhance the quality of the Early Childhood Educators training event and the teaching units by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Participation in this study is voluntary. All information provided will be confidential and participants' anonymity will be protected throughout the study. IP addresses will not be collected at any point, meaning the data you provide cannot be traced back to the participant. The results of the evaluation process will be published without sharing any information about the respondents in an open access publication in the frame of the EduPASS European project.

Part 1: General Information

1.1. What is your age?

1.2. What is your gender?

1.3. Country

1.4. University / Faculty / Department / Organization

1.5. Are you currently practising any sport? Yes No

1.6. Have you practised any sport in the past? Yes No

1.7. If you answered **YES** in one of the previous questions (1.5 and/or 1.6), what is/was the main sport that you have been practicing?

Type of sport: _____

1.8. How many years have you been practicing this sport?

_____ years

1.9. What is your major achievement in this sport (e.g., awards, competitions on local, district, regional, national, international level)?

1.10. Are you currently an early childhood educator-developer? Yes No

1.11. Have you worked as early childhood educator-developer in the past? Yes No

1.12. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), in which sport(s) have you been early childhood educator-developer?

Type of sport(s): _____

1.13. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), for how many years have you been an early childhood educator-developer?

_____ years

1.14. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.10 and/or 1.11), which topic(s)/module(s) have you been teaching?

1.15. Do you currently work as early childhood educator? Yes No

1.16. Have you worked in the past as early childhood educator? Yes No

1.17. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.15 and/or 1.16), what is/was the main sport that you have been teaching?

1.18. If you answered **YES** in the previous questions (1.15 and/or 1.16), for how many years have you been an early childhood educator?

_____ years

1.19. If you answered **YES** in the previous question (1.15 and/or 1.16), what age groups do you primarily teach?

Children (under the age of 12 years)

Adolescents (ages 13-17 years old)

Young adults (18-25 years)

Adults (over 25 years)

1.20. If you answered **YES** in the previous question (1.15 and/or 1.16), what is the athletes' level that you primarily teach?

Recreational

Competitive

Elite

Professional

1.21. Have you attended any early childhood educator training/courses in the past? Yes No

1.22. If you have attended, briefly describe what this training was about.

1.23. Do you have a bachelor and/or master's (or respective equivalent academic university) degree in sport science and/or physical education?

No

Yes, I have a bachelor's degree

Yes, I have a master's degree

Yes, I have an equivalent academic university degree

Part 2: Early Childhood Educators training event

To ensure the quality of the event as well as improving it, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions. Please select the most relevant answer for each statement.

2.1. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the early childhood educators training event?

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
Organizational aspects						
2.1.1 The event was adequately and logically structured.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.2 The event was well designed.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.3 The time frame of the event was appropriate.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.4 The event was delivered at an appropriate pace/rhythm.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.5 The materials and resources were well prepared.	<input type="radio"/>					
Teaching and content						
2.1.6 The content was presented in a clear and understandable way.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.7 The teaching enabled the learners to attain the learning outcomes.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.8 The learners seemed to enjoy the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.9 The learners engaged and actively participated during the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.10 The overall topic of the event referred well to the practice.	<input type="radio"/>					

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.1.11 The specific content of the event referred well to the practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.12 The topics were discussed sufficiently.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.13 I was able to improve my knowledge and skills related to the topics discussed.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.14 The content will be helpful to me as an early childhood educator-developer.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.15 The teaching units of the event are compatible with the national coaching framework.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.16 I gained new knowledge and information for my teaching practice from the event.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.18 The topic and content presented in the event was new to me.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.1.19 I enjoyed the event.	<input type="radio"/>					

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the implementation and feasibility of the early childhood educators training event?

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree	N/A
2.2.1	The event motivated me to consider implementing the contents in my teaching.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.2	I will use the materials and resources which I received in the event in my future lessons and teaching.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.3	I can imagine myself implementing EduPASS resources with other future early childhood educators.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.4	I believe that the sport club environment will be supportive for the implementation of the EduPASS resources.	<input type="radio"/>					
2.2.5	I consider the EduPASS resources useful as they can be easily implemented during teaching.	<input type="radio"/>					

		Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
2.3.	I would recommend this early childhood educators training event to other early childhood educator-developers and early childhood educators.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the early childhood educators training event

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future early childhood educators. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the early childhood educators training event that you think is relevant.

The BEST features of the early childhood educators training event were:

I did NOT like the following:

I would like to see the following CHANGES:

I have specific comments for this early childhood educators training event:

Teaching unit Title:	Teaching unit Code:
-----------------------------	----------------------------

Date:

Part 3: Teaching unit content

3.4. Indicate your level of satisfaction with each of the following items by selecting the most relevant answer.

	1 ☹	2	3	4	5 ☺	N/A
RATING: 1 = Very Dissatisfied 2 = Dissatisfied 3 = Neutral 4 = Satisfied 5 = Very Satisfied						
3.1.1 The overall teaching of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.2 The delivery of the teaching unit (e.g., lectures, practical sessions, group discussions, sharing of ideas and experiences, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.3 The pedagogical approaches presented to teaching sports.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.4 The description of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.5 The content of the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.6 The clarity of the teaching unit content.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.7 The balance between theory and practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.8 The defined learning outcomes and/or objectives were adequately explained.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.9 The learning materials (e.g., handouts, workshop material, case studies, websites, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.10 The appropriateness of the assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.11 The explanation of the assessment criteria.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.12 The assessment methods effectiveness in identifying early childhood educators' strengths and areas for future development.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.13 The communication of the learning outcomes and assessment model.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.14 The collaboration through shared knowledge with peers.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.15 The overall workload (achievable, realistic, adequate).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.16 The effectiveness of the teaching unit in raising early childhood educators' professional development.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.17 The quality of the support given by the teaching staff on assignments.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.18 The preparation of the teaching staff.	<input type="radio"/>					

3.1.19	The approachability and support of teaching staff (i.e., instructive, inspiring, encouraging, and motivating).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.20	The organisational arrangements for the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.21	The relevance of the teaching unit in raising early childhood educators' professional development (knowledge and practice).	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.22	The transferability of the lessons learnt in the teaching unit to practice.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.23	The development of new skills and/or teaching strategies due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.24	The increase of my motivation to learn due to this teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.25	The overall knowledge gained by the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					
3.1.26	My overall satisfaction with the teaching unit.	<input type="radio"/>					

	Disagree	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Agree
3.2. I would recommend this teaching unit to other early childhood educator-developers and early childhood educators.	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments about the teaching unit

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future early childhood educators. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the teaching unit that you think is relevant.

The BEST features of the teaching unit were:

I did NOT like the following:

I would like to see the following CHANGES:

I have specific comments for this teaching unit:

I will try to implement these teaching unit's topics (maximum 3) in my teaching practice: